

‘CRYING ON THE INTERNET FOR VALID REASONS’: EMOTIONAL ENGAGEMENTS WITH ‘SAD GIRL MUSIC’ ON TIKTOK

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Abstract: A TikTok posted in reaction to indie rock band boygenius’ song ‘Letter to an Old Poet’ shows a young person looking melancholically at the camera, with the caption stating, ‘crying on the internet for valid reasons.’ Recently, TikTok has been flooded with similar videos of mostly young queer women showing themselves crying in reaction to so-called ‘sad girl music’: a contested term referring to music that explores ‘ordinary’ sad feelings. Utilizing familiar fandom practices like reaction videos, these TikToks connect the music to queer youths’ own emotional states, their identities, and broader societal issues. Based in fandom, queer, and affect theory, this paper explores how emotions, and especially sadness, are mobilized in sad girl music fandom on TikTok. Conducting a visual and critical discourse analysis of TikToks collected using the platform’s sound feature, I examine how TikTok’s affordances of templatability and circumscribed creativity encourage emotional engagements with music and how these become part of fandom-specific platform vernacular practices. Building on Cvetkovich’s conception of depression (2012) and Ahmed’s sociality of sadness (2014), I further analyze how these music fandom practices facilitate collective identity constructions and experiences of sadness, function as coping mechanisms, and what they reveal about queer youths’ expectations for the future in the context of ongoing socio-political crises. Overarchingly, this presentation contributes to understandings of the role of emotions and affects in platformed music fandoms.

Keywords: platformed music fandom, emotions and affect, TikTok, mental health, queer identity constructions, sad girl music

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Introduction

In a TikTok posted on March 31, 2023, a young person wearing headphones, sitting in a room decorated with music posters, looks at the camera with a melancholic expression on her face while the song 'Letter to an Old Poet' by indie rock supergroup boygenius plays. The creator sings along and reacts to the music, her facial expressions and hand movements expressing various emotions, from sadness to subtle amusement. Overlaying the video is the text 'why on earth would they make this song. they must have no concern whatsoever for my wellbeing!', with the caption stating 'crying on the internet for valid reasons'. This video is one of many posted on the social media platform TikTok in reaction to the release of boygenius' album *the record*. It is one example of how, in the past few years, TikTok has regularly been flooded with videos set to what is called 'sad girl music' (Zoladz, 2022): a contested term referring to music exploring 'ordinary' sad feelings. Utilizing familiar fandom practices like reaction videos, these TikToks connect the music to queer youths' own emotional states, their identities, and broader societal issues.

In this paper, I examine these fandom practices, exploring how emotions are mobilized in queer youth's sad girl music fandom on TikTok. Conducting a critical discourse analysis of TikToks collected using the platform's sound feature, I analyse how queer youth understand their sadness in relation to sad girl music and how queer youth engage with the music on TikTok. First, I argue that queer youth's use of fandom practices and platform affordances function as tools of identity- and community-formation, particularly for queer fans. Second, building on affect theory, I argue that expressions of sadness within these fan engagements function as a way to understand and process emotions within socio-political contexts, facilitating connections and bearing potential for political engagements. Overall, this paper highlights the increasing connections between music fandom, queer identity constructions, emotions, and political engagements in the platform context.

Background & Methodology

The term sad girl music has emerged in popular discourses as a simultaneously contested and empowering term referring to music that explores 'everyday longing and disappointment' (Tolentino, 2018). The artists most often associated with sad girl music are largely working within the indie rock and indie folks genres (Geisel, 2021), with Julien Baker, Phoebe Bridgers, and Lucy Dacus (who together make up the band boygenius), and Mitski, as some of the most prominent names who I focus on. As the term suggests, sad girl music is embedded in discourses of sadness and mental health, and it is part of a broader recent social inclination towards greater awareness of mental health issues and sadness that has emerged over the past decade within the mainstream (Thelandersson, 2023). Its most common use is as an informal descriptor of music by mostly female musicians, many of whom are queer, that makes reference to (negative) emotions, and particularly negative emotions (Garcia-Furtado, 2022). At the same time, understandings of the term have also been influenced by its increased popularity in the context of a music industry dominated by platforms, and phenomena like the popular Spotify-curated playlist 'sad girl starter pack' (Spotify, n.d.). This playlist exemplifies how the music's exploration of various emotions and ideas is often reduced to sadness in a way that

depoliticizes and commodifies (female) emotion. While the term is thus highly contested and associated artists have criticized it, it is still prominent on TikTok.

With affect and emotions central to engagements with the music on TikTok, my analysis is guided by affect theory, queer theory, and feminist theory. I situate sad girl music and culture in the context of a society marked by neoliberal capitalism and postfeminism (Gill, 2007) in which the achievement of happiness and well-being is posited as an individual responsibility (Ahmed, 2010) and everyday life produces feelings of despair and anxiety (Cvetkovich, 2012).

Fan studies provide another important framework for studying sad girl music TikToks, highlighting how participation in fandom can be an important part of identity formation and meaning making (Grossberg, 1992; Jenkins, 1992; Lewis, 1992). Particularly for queer people, being a fan of something presents possibilities for identity formation, as well as for finding queer community (Valentine, 1995). In this context, the short video based social media platform TikTok provides a particularly conducive space for both queer users and for music fandom. The personalized For You Page (FYP) of content based on the platform's recommendation algorithm (Zhao, 2021) and the app's sound feature that allows users to easily incorporate music and sounds into their videos (Kaye et al., 2022, pp. 23, 32) open novel ways for fan and listening communities to engage with music and one another, allowing them to express their identity in relation to artists and music, as well as to find community. TikTok's focus on repetition and imitation produce new forms of sociality and connection between users (Zulli & Zulli, 2022).

Due to the centrality of the FYP and the sound feature to TikTok's specificity and affordances, my methodology is guided by 'research that follows the medium' (Rogers, 2015, p. 23) and uses TikTok's embedded functions as primary modes of data collection. Creating a TikTok account, I used the sound feature as the main input for training the algorithm by going to specific sounds (boygenius/Mitski songs) to watch and collect content. The analytical approach for analysing the final data set of 222 TikToks was informed by critical technocultural discourse analysis (Brock, 2012, 2018, 2020) and critical discourse analysis (Wodak, 2001). Following the main phase of data collection, I carried out two rounds of qualitative coding informed by feminist constructivist grounded theory (Charmaz, 2008). Conducting a critical discourse analysis of the collected videos, I pay close attention to how the TikToks engage in discourses around sad girl music, how their expressions relate to broader contexts, and how they exist within and make use of the specific platform context.

Findings

The analysis of the collected sad girl music TikToks reveals two overarching themes: fandom practices as identity construction, and the different levels and functions of emotional expressions.

(Queer) Fandom Practices and Identity Construction in the Platform Context

Within the examined sad girl music TikToks, music functions as a tool for constructing identity. On social media, identifying as a fan has long been a way to represent one's identity. People construct their identity through association with

music, celebrities, and cultural artifacts, using these associations to both understand their own identity and to express it to the outside world. As Grossberg (1992) writes: 'the fan gives authority to that which he or she invests in, letting the object of such investments speak for and as him or herself' (p. 59). While the centrality of identity in fandom practices is thus not new or limited to sad girl music on TikTok, queer youth's engagements with the music on the platform reiterate how, shaped by TikTok's affordances and features, music fandom practices are an important part of identity-formation and expression, and being a fan of openly queer artists like boygenius can especially serve as explorations and expressions of queer identity and sexuality.

Collective Identity Construction

By engaging with the music on TikTok, users position themselves as fans of boygenius, Mitski, or sad girl music more broadly. More than just signifying their enjoyment of the music, these self-identifications invoke specific identity markers. In turn, these serve as objects of recognition between fans and contribute to the construction of a collective 'sad girl music fan' identity. At large, this collective sad girl music fan identity revolves around emotions and mental health, queerness, sexuality, and shared affective objects associated with the music and is facilitated by the repetition of certain recurring discourses, attributes, and conventions or formats of posts. While there are some variations in the kinds of identities depicted and how they are constructed, the TikToks in my dataset overarchingly conceptualize the sad girl music fan as a young queer woman or nonbinary person struggling with mental health issues who relates to the music on an emotional level. Shaped by broader fandom practices and TikTok's platform vernacular, the most common format of sad girl music TikToks are videos of users showing themselves emotionally reacting to (newly released) music as exemplified in the TikTok mentioned at the beginning. By showcasing their emotions in response to the music and implicating the artists as responsible for these emotions, the creator makes use of fandom practices and TikTok's affordances of replicability to express their emotions in a register they know will be understood by other fans within this specific context and affirms their identity as a fan. These expressions of intense emotions thus contribute to the construction of a coherent sad girl music fan identity. As Zulli & Zulli argue in their conceptualization of imitation publics, it is 'through the shared ritual of content imitation and replication' (2022, p. 1882) that people on TikTok in particular are able to connect and feel a sense of community. By taking part in the repetition of these expressions, folks on TikTok both construct their own identity as legible to others, allowing them to feel connected to fandom cultures, and reiterate and consequently legitimize the broader conception of what it means to be a sad girl music fan.

Music & Queer Life Narratives

While queerness is a central part of collective fandom identity, music and representations provided by music and artists can further contribute to fans' individual explorations of lesbian and queer identities and ability to envision queer life narratives for themselves: 'music unfolds queer possibilities' (Driver, 2007, p. 216). In the TikTok content, lesbian identity is often humorously constructed in specific relation to sad girl music. One 2-picture slideshow TikTok strategically uses the platform's slideshow feature to create this association between being a lesbian and a boygenius fan. The first picture depicts the lesbian flag and reads 'im a lesb',

denoting a specific identity statement, but when one then scrolls to the second image, instead of completing the word 'lesbian' the text builds on the last letter 'b' of the first image and completes as 'oygenius fan' over a picture of the band. This TikTok quite literally fuses lesbian identity and boygenius fandom, making them textually inseparable. Reminiscent of identificatory phrases like 'friend of Dorothy', 'k. d. lang fan', or the more recent 'do you listen to girl in red?', boygenius fandom can similarly act as lesbian code for people on TikTok and draws explicit attention to lesbian identities. Considering the ways in which lesbian identities have long been invisibilized (Jagose, 1994, 2002; Nešović, 2021), the focus on queer and particularly lesbian identities and desire within sad girl music fandom practices on TikTok is significant as it disrupts lesbian invisibility and simultaneously reshapes familiar fandom practices that are commonly heteronormative and male-centered.

Fandom's potential to meaningfully contribute to identity construction and meaning-making is further reflected in a boygenius fandom-specific TikTok trend in which creators relate their individual development over five years to the release of boygenius' music. Using TikTok's slideshow feature and set to a song by the band, these posts consist of two images of the creator where the first one depicts them in 2018 with the text 'me when the boygenius ep came out,' and a second photo of the creator in March 2023 with the text 'me when the record came out'. By contrasting images of themselves at these different times, the creators highlight changes in their personal expression (e.g., hair styles, tattoos, or clothing choices) that become 'queerer' over time. One TikTok using this trend, hashtagged #transmasc, depicts the creator's transition process. Celebrating their transition, this example illustrates how engaging with music and in fandom can be a transformative experience that supports identity construction. Queer artists and their music provide important representation and contribute to queer youths' envisioning of queer life narratives.

Affects, Societal Contexts, and Political Potentials of Sad Girl Music TikToks

Moving on to the second part of my analysis, I look specifically at how emotions are expressed in sad girl music TikToks. My findings show how emotions in sad girl music TikToks function on multiple different levels: the individual, the community, the societal, and the political level.

Returning to the TikTok I started out with, the caption 'crying on the internet for valid reasons' encapsulates how engaging with sad girl music can provide fans with a way for expressing their own emotions, as well as for processing these emotions. Research has long found music to be able to affect mood and emotional states, showing how music can trigger negative feelings, and also work as a coping mechanism to deal with negative feelings (Saarikallio & Erkkilä, 2007). A common thread in my TikTok dataset involved instances of creators comparing music to therapy or medication, such as through the hashtag '#mitskiistherapy'. Similar to going to therapy to cope with depression or anxiety, these TikToks posit that listening to music can provide 'a source of survival and affirmation' (Driver, 2007, p. 226).

Intimate Publics and Sociality of Sadness

Posting about emotions elevates them to a social level. Posting a TikTok of oneself crying or expressing negative emotions in some other way also asks for one's

emotions to be recognized, to be witnessed by others. Sara Ahmed writes ‘there is a connection between the over-representation of pain and its unrepresentability’ in that, while one may not be able to ‘describe “adequately” the feelings of pain’, they may evoke this pain again and again (Ahmed, 2014, p. 22). In my TikTok dataset, the pain of negative feelings is repeatedly evoked in recurring ways; largely through showing the creator crying or through assertions that they are not doing well. These repeated statements of pain illustrate the unrepresentability of pain while also highlighting the creators’ desire of being able to convey their pain to others, of having their pain be witnessed.

One TikTok posted shortly after the release of boygenius’ record features the caption ‘how is everyone feeling. i am not ok’, expressing both the creator’s own emotions in response to the music, and the creator’s concern for other listeners’ emotional well-being. In this way, the creator simultaneously asks for others to witness her pain, while also wanting to bear witness to others’ pain. While it is never possible to truly know someone else’s pain, by witnessing their pain, it is granted ‘the status of an event, a happening in the world’ (Ahmed, 2014, p. 29), and it is this desire for their sadness to be witnessed that becomes apparent in many sad girl music TikToks. At the same time, the caption ‘how is everyone feeling’ invokes an assumed community of fans that contributes to the formation of an intimate public (Berlant, 2008) centred around an affect of sadness. Even when people expressing their emotions don’t actually have the exact same experiences, the similarities in their affective reactions, the similarities in affect, are what create a sense of belonging between them (Muchitsch, 2024, p. 239).

Societal Contexts

Further, queer youth’s expressions of emotion in relation to the music on TikTok allow them to understand their individual struggles with mental illness as part of socio-political structures. Following Cvetkovich’s understanding of depression as a public feeling produced by the conditions of everyday life under neoliberal capitalism, I argue that creators make connections between their sadness and the societal context they live in. One TikTok set to Mitski’s ‘Working for the Knife’, a song reflecting on the pressures of everyday life and unfulfilled dreams, shows a young person singing along to the lyrics with an exasperated expression overlaid by the caption ‘mitski really wrote this song for all the people that started working really young (13-17) and then could never stop. you sell whats left of your childhood for \$13 an hour’ with the caption ‘once you start working you really never stop’. By linking the song to their experiences of having to start working at a young age, the TikTok points to an awareness of capitalism’s impact on people’s mental states and feelings of sadness. The song allows the creator to understand their own experiences in relation to broader societal contexts.

Similarly, many of the TikToks within my dataset convey the creators’ feelings of disillusionment with the future, feeling like the future that was promised isn’t available to them anymore. One TikTok draws attention to the lyric ‘it hurts to hope the future/ Will be better than before’ from boygenius’ song ‘Afraid of Heights’. The popularity of sad girl music among queer youth thus highlights how the continued attachment to a future state of happiness can be painful, they express, how one TikTok puts it, ‘sadness for a future that has disappeared’.

Political Potentials

With connections to socio-political contexts already present in the TikToks, some TikToks in my dataset directly link the music and emotions to politics, showing how emotions may function as a starting point for more explicitly political engagements where sad girl music becomes associated with left-wing politics. One TikTok consisting of videos of Mitski screaming into the microphone during live performances features the text 'maturing is realizing it isn't just who's president, it's america as a whole'. Instead of specifically making connections between that statement and the lyrics, the TikTok creates an affective association between Mitski's rage and general discontent with the American political system. As such, in this TikTok, emotions themselves function as a political expression.

By being exposed to political content on their FYP, sad girl music listeners can come to associate political ideas with the music and the emotional videos they are already engaging with (Thelandersson, 2023, p. 183). Even when not directly invoking the lyrics, TikToks combining images of artists and music with political expressions allow audiences to become attuned to political thought. These associations are further strengthened by artists' own political expressions, such as boygenius' support of queer and trans people and their protest against anti-drag legislations by performing in drag at their 2023 concert in Tennessee (Ruiz & Hussey, 2023). These expressions create an assumption of shared political values within fandom spaces which, in turn, facilitates drawing attention to specific political causes by using sounds, knowing that political content will likely be met with support due to the fandom's overarching affects and values. In one such TikTok raising awareness about the situation of queer Palestinians in Gaza living through Israeli occupation and genocide, the use of a Mitski song and the caption's reference to crying evokes sadness in a way that aligns with the overarching affect of sadness in sad girl music TikTok, but redirects that sadness away from the personal toward the political. Thus, even though sad girl music TikToks are for the most part not directly focused on politics, through exposure to political ideas and values in the specific context of sad girl music engagements, audiences can nonetheless come to political consciousness.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study of queer youth's sad girl music fandom on TikTok demonstrates how queer youth use fandom practices and platform affordances as tools for identity- and community-formation. It further illustrates how expressions of sadness can function as way to understand and process emotions within socio-political contexts, how they can facilitate connections and have potential for political engagements. Overall, this research highlights the increasing connections between music fandom, queer identity constructions, emotions, and political engagements in the platform context. It underscores the role of emotions and affects in platformed music fandoms where collective experiences of sadness and shared affective investments can facilitate engagements with socio-political contexts.

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